

Recommendation 17:

Using 'Gamification' to meet the public sector need 'Employee remuneration and incentives'

Status quo:

Generally speaking, gamification can be part of every organization's digital business strategy. Within the public sector, gamification can be used to help public agencies run communication campaigns, raise awareness of new or undervalued initiatives, engage citizens, train officials and even change behaviour. To meet the need 'Employee remuneration and incentives', gamification can be used as a way to motivate public employees. Adding game elements to the job is expected to raise motivation, as players take on challenges, receive immediate feedback on their performance, and can compete against others. Building self-esteem and re-enforcing it with peer recognition is a powerful means of unlocking motivation.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Cyber security, as gamified processes generate a track record of employees' achievements and the collection and use of personally identifiable data

Non-technical challenges:

- *Process:* The challenge does not lie in the infrastructure, but in the design of the game. It requires a solid and user-centred process (fun scenario building a genuine sense of competition)
- *Acceptance:* There are gamification detractors that fear it's just another form of control.
- *Organisation:* Games by their nature must be voluntary, so when a department insists its employees play along, it stops being a game to be a form of coercion
- *Social issue:* With regards to peer relationships, efforts to increase internal competition could provoke employees to actively sabotage each other or make unethical choices

Employee remuneration and incentives:

When given the choice to improve one aspect of their own job, 36 percent of our public sector informants cited pay, 26 percent said career development, 11 percent said their pension and 81 percent said their organisation had not changed its recruitment practices in light of greater collaboration with the private sector. Sub-needs under this domain include: offering rewards and benefits based on periodic evaluations, pay for performance, getting rid of ineffective incentives systems, formulating a collective wage agreement and offering job security. Certain quotes to highlight the concerns of informants are: "Distorted incentive systems.", "The wages are quite low in comparison with the industry sector.", "Make public sector jobs more attractive, like offering apartments or retirement provisions."

Gamification:

Gamification is the use of game mechanics to drive engagement in non-game business scenarios and to change behaviours in a target audience to achieve business outcomes. Game mechanics such as points, challenges, leaderboards, rules and incentives that make game-play enjoyable are included in these gamified processes.